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LIVED EXPERIENCES OF UPLAND TEACHERS DURING CALAMITIES: BASES FOR PROGRAM RECOMMENDATION

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Abstract

With a constructivist perspective under phenomenological process, the research study aimed to determine the lived experiences of upland teacher during calamities in Schools District of Tubungan, Schools Division of Iloilo. A thematic analysis was used to analyze the collected qualitative data through in-depth interview using researcher-made interview guide. Three main themes were identified: (1) Upland Teachers Lived Experiences; (2) Challenges of upland Teachers During calamities; (3) Coping Strategies of Upland Teachers During Calamities. Six recommendation programs were conceptualized and considered based on the prevailing parameters from the three main themes: (1) Hazard Pay-Recipient Program; (2) Free Transportation Program; (3) Three School Center Program; (4) School Parent Teachers Association Meeting; and (5) Debriefing on Children's Awareness on Disaster Preparedness; (6) Seminar and Training for School Heads.

Keywords: Upland Teachers, Experiences, Calamities, Recommendation Program

1. Introduction

One of the nation's most vulnerable to natural disasters in the globe is the Philippines. Situated at the epicenter of a typhoon belt and on the edge of two major tectonic plates, its islands frequently experience landslides, floods, typhoons, earthquakes, volcanoes, and droughts.

Teaching in remote barangays during natural disasters is a significant challenge for us as upland educators. Upland teachers have experienced a variety of things, such as riding motorcycles during wet days, crossing barangays that are prone to landslides, traveling kilometers to get to school safely, and dealing with intense rain and wind because of their topographical location.

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Even though authorities have a lengthy history of dealing with disasters and have robust coping strategies. However, there are still large disparities in the ability to manage disasters among the various parts of the nation.

Considering these facts, the researcher ascertained the Program Recommendation within the Tubungan Schools District and the Lived Experiences of Upland Teachers During Calamities.

2. Research Method

The present study used a descriptive research methodology, utilizing in-depth interviews to elicit the perspectives of participants.

This study used a phenomenological technique in a qualitative research design.

Purposive sampling, sometimes referred to as judgement sampling, is a technique in which informants are deliberately chosen for their special features.

The research instrument used in the study was a researcher-made interview guide.

A team of experts in testing, evaluation, and research conducted the validation procedure for the interview schedule that the researcher had created.

The participants of the study were ten (10) upland teachers at the Schools District of Tubungan identified through purposive and convenient sampling techniques.

3. Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

The Lived Experiences of Upland Teachers During Calamities

Natural Calamities. The result implies that upland teachers experienced natural calamities such as floods, earthquakes, and typhoons. Thus, it burdens them in coming to school. It conformed with the study of (Anderson, 2010) that it threatens the physical safety and psychological well-being of the communities, not just that it also interrupts the educational continuity.

Fires and Arm Conflict. The outcome suggests that upland teachers have been affected by man-made disasters like fires and armed warfare, putting their lives in jeopardy and making it dangerous for them to go to and from work. It complied with (Utsumi, 2022) study, which found that it has both direct and indirect consequences on actors, students, and other educational institutions, as well as (Jones and Naylor, 2014) recognition of the ways in which arm conflict impacts education and the learning process.

Challenges of Upland Teachers During Calamities

Risk to Travel. The result implies that after disasters, teachers in the upland school are more impacted than those in the lowlands. The school's location presents them with a number of

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challenges, and one of their main worries is the risk of traveling. Teachers in highland communities with muddy, landslide-prone roads run the risk of moving and using their motorcycles as their primary source of transportation to get to school. The outcome supported research by (Wisner, 2012) that found disasters could cause damage to infrastructure, including highways.

Technical Problem. The result implies that during natural disasters, upland teachers encounter technological issues including power disruptions and erratic internet connections, which led to misunderstandings and delayed submission of online reports, thus impeding their ability to impart knowledge.

Coping Strategies of Upland Teachers During Calamities

Being Prepared. The result implies that having a plan and taking personal responsibility for your safety as well as the safety of your learners were crucial elements that will enable you to deal with the fallout from disasters and continue to provide instruction to your learners. The community and school need to prepare the emergency supplies needed in case of a disaster. The study supported the research of (McIvor and Paton, 2012), who found that communities in high-risk areas should take precautionary steps since disasters can strike at any time.

Community Awareness. The result implies that one method to deal with the difficulties brought on by disasters is to get ready and assist your community in doing the same. This supports the finding of (Magunda, 2010) that behavior changes brought about by public awareness campaigns promote a culture of risk minimization.

Disaster Preparedness Trainings. The result implies that attending disaster preparedness seminars, trainings, and the like were crucial to create a community free of casualties before, during, and after disasters. It conformed to the study of (Newport and Jawahar, 2003) that disaster preparedness is useless without the involvement of institutions and vulnerable communities.

Early Announcement. This implies that to prevent teachers from residing in other barangays from traveling on routes that are prone to disasters to go to school, appropriate authorities must promptly notify the cancellation of classes. This was in line with (Col, 2007) study, which stated that the local government's duty is to act in a way that is appropriate for the residents. This involves communicating with them and providing a memorandum on the subject.

The following were the program recommendations to help upland teachers during calamities: Hazard Pay-Recipient Program by the Local Government Unit (LGU) through Special Education Fund (SEF), Free Transportation Program by the Local Government Unit (LGU) through Special Education Fund (SEF), Three School Center Program, School Parent Teachers Association Collaboration, Debriefing on Children for Awareness Program and Seminar and Training for School Heads.

4. Insights

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In phenomenological stance as surmised from the three main themes, the following insights were drawn:

Risk of travelling was evident among participants' interview transcripts. Almost all of them struggles in travelling to school during natural calamities and man-made calamities. Experiencing typhoon, flash floods, landslides, and heavy rains, burning of grasses in the mountains and ambush incident were the lived experiences of upland teachers in schools district of Tubungan.

A sad reality and challenge of upland teachers as mentioned by the participants were staying at a community for a week and being away to their family. It is hard for them to go home every day because of the distance. Despite of the instances, teachers still enjoy their stay with co-teachers, beautiful sceneries, and the culture of the "tumandok" the Panay Bukidnon Tribe.

Moreover, technical Problem such as power outages, no cellular signal and internet connection hinders upland teachers in getting information and submitting online reports on time.

Upland teachers find ways to maintain their emotional and mental health despite the multiple effects of natural and man-made calamities they experienced.

Passion for teaching, love for upland learners and their commitment to work as their motivation in accepting challenges brought by natural and man-made calamities.

5. Recommendations

Based on the outcomes and results of the research, the researchers would like to recommend the following:

Teachers should be provided with the necessary support needed in ensuring their safety and safety of their learners as well, during natural and man-made calamities. Thus, a Hazard Pay Recipient Program can compensate the efforts of teachers in teaching in the upland school.

Local Government Unit should also ensure the large support for upland-based schools, especially to teachers teaching in upland school should be the recipient of Free Transportation Program by the Local Government Unit (LGU) through Special Education Fund (SEF), this will aid the burden of teachers from travelling kilometers away from home to school. This will help the teachers in continuing the passion of teaching and producing a great professional indigenous people someday.

Three School Center Program in cooperation with Local Government Unit (LGU), by putting up facility which upland teachers can access uninterrupted internet connection that will help them in receiving real-time information and by sending online reports without the hassle of internet connectivity. Through this program the problem in receiving information about the cancellation of classes and other programs that will benefit the school will be lessen.

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School Parent Teachers involvement in the uniformity of information should also be considered. With proper collaboration in disseminating information would greatly benefit the organization. Through this, parent would check on the welfare of their children by preparing them from upcoming disasters and teaching them what to do during those circumstances.

The School Heads and Principals should consistently participate and conduct and be involve in the disaster preparedness workshops, trainings and drills so upland teachers and learners are equipped with basic skills and strategies that will help them during, before and after the calamity.

That the upland students, should evaluate and execute their learnings about disaster preparedness from their teacher in times of disaster occurrence, and as they learned about it, they should share this to their community.

Deped Officials and Program Manager should investigate the curriculum and review its features pertaining Hazard Pay for upland teachers. They should design, create, and implement programs that promotes the general welfare and holistic development of teachers.

That the future researchers, should conduct similar or related studies on the lived experiences of upland teachers during calamities and be recommended with proper programs for their well-being.

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